

Assessing the Impact of Intercropping on Maize and Cowpea Yields in Aynayaskax Village, Garowe District, Puntland, Somalia

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Abstract:

The field experiment was carried out during the March 2023 -May 2024 cropping season at Aynayaskax village, Garowe district, Somalia to determine the effect of intercropping of maize and cowpea on the yield, land use efficiency, and profitability of both crops. The experiment consisted of 2 treatments (sole maize, sole cowpea, in two replications where intercrop 1 (spacing of 40 cm between maize and cowpea) and intercrop 2 (spacing of 30 cm between maize and cowpea served as treatments.). The study revealed that while sole cropping of maize resulted in the highest grain yield (4245.4 kg ha⁻¹), intercropping systems also yielded respectable results. Based on the present finding, intercropping of

one row of maize and one row of cowpea has more economic advantage than the other crop combination or grown alone. Therefore, intercropping of one-row maize to one row of cowpea is advantageous to farmers in the study area since it would provide additional crop yield with the same piece of land and be more profitable related to cost-benefit. Therefore, intercropping of one-row maize to one-row cowpea is advantageous to farmers in the study area since it would provide additional crop yield with the same piece of land and more profit related to cost benefit.

Keywords: *Intercropping, Cowpeas, Maize, Yield, Aynayaskax, Village, Garowe, Puntland, Somalia.*

Introduction

Attaining food and nutritional security for millions of people worldwide is one of the most stressful challenges, particularly for limited agricultural countries, such as Somalia Otekunrin, O. A. (2024). Climate change often creates additional threats to agricultural production. Since it is one of the most vulnerable countries to flood, drought, and diseases (Suhi, et al., 2022). Crop diversification can improve soil fertility and water-use efficiency, and maintain natural enemies of

insect pests, while a monoculture system with a single species (Abdul Rahman et al., 2023).

Moreover, a diversified cropping system is not only a resilient and sustainable crop production technique but it also provides large varieties of food with different nutritional qualities to the farmers (Brooker et al., 2016). Intercropping is a well-known practice of diversified cropping systems and therefore, it could provide similar benefits. For instance, it can efficiently use growth resources, including nutrients, light, and water, thus maintaining soil health. Intercropping is the simultaneous growing of

two or more crops in the same field. Farmers practice different cropping systems to increase productivity and sustainability (Himmelstein et al., 2017).

A Cropping system that reduces weed population may provide a weed-suppressive foundation upon which cultural weed control could be laid. The use of intercropping by smallholder and peasant farmers is a common practice that dates back to ancient civilizations in the tropics and rain-fed areas of the world (Tilman, 2020). The advantages of intercropping include soil conservation, lodging resistance, yield increment, and weed control over monocropping (Zhang et al., 2020).

Maize intercropping with Cowpea plays an important role in subsistence food production in both developed and developing countries, especially in situations of limited water resources like Somalia country. Intercropping of maize with cowpea crops helps maintain and improve soil fertility and plays an important role in subsistence food production in developing countries because farmers cannot afford inorganic fertilizers (Yang and Chai, 2018). Intercropping Maize with cowpea are a potential source of plant nutrients that compliment/supplement inorganic fertilizers. Maize with cowpea intercrops has several socioeconomic, and biological and ecological advantages compared to sole cropping for smallholder farmers. In addition, certain legumes crops provide food to humans and livestock (Jensen et al., 2020).

In Somalia, where agriculture continues to play a significant role in the economy and people's livelihoods, it is crucial to optimize farming techniques to enhance productivity while maintaining environmental sustainability. Cultivating multiple crops together or intercropping can provide numerous benefits, including improved soil health and crop yield by mitigating competition for resources such as land, space, light interception, and nutrition. This study examined the prevalent and culturally important practice of intercropping maize with cowpea in many African countries, including Somalia. There are several intercrop

arrangements which may include row intercropping worldwide but in Somalia, there was any information related to Maize intercropping with Cowpea as experiment study (Dong et al., 2018).

On other hand this experiment was engaged at the community level and involved various inputs, such as seeds, labor, and fertilizer. The resulting crop yields benefited the community of Aynayaskax Village by decreasing their reliance on chemical inputs and reducing market costs. These benefits, though indirect, contributed to the overall well-being of the village. The aim was to assess the benefits and potential challenges of intercropping with traditional monoculture techniques was to determine the effect of intercropping and planting patterns on the performance of maize and cowpeas in semi-arid Aynaskax village.

Objectives

1. Evaluate the efficiency of maize and cowpea when cultivated together in an intercropping system compared to their cultivation as distinct monocultures in Aynayaskax Village .
2. Examine the impact of intercropping on soil quality and pest management.
3. Evaluate the economic viability of using intercropping methods in the area by compares the cost benefit analysis of intercropping and monoculture system.
4. To evaluate the economic benefits or challenges of using intercropping techniques, it is important to consider the current market conditions, availability of resources, and socio-economic factors that impact farmers' decision-making.

Materials and Methods

Description of the Study Area

The experiment was conducted at the research field at Aynaskax village in Garowe district, East Africa University, Garowe, with the Collaborate Ministry of Agricultural and Irrigation carrying out the experimental study under the Kaaftoomiye component project, Action for

Improved Resilience, Food, Nutrition, and Income Security in Puntland (CAIRFNISPP) 2023-2025, which was financially supported in this research study. This study was part of the University of Teaching and Research experiment program in the Department of Agricultural and Veterinary Medicine.

The study was carried out at Aynaskax village in Garowe district between the growth seasons/cropping season of March 2023 and May 2024 during the Dayr season. Aynaskax village in Garowe district has a hot desert climate with temperatures ranging from 23 to 25°C. The geographical location field is between 8.408416 and 48.483723 latitude and longitude and 450 m above sea level. The area receives 108mm of annual rainfall, with the highest average being 51mm in May. The soil is poor, making it challenging for sustainable farming. The village primarily grows lemon, papaya, date palm, onion, melon, and vegetable crops.

Experimental Design, Layout, and Treatments

The plots were later laid out and treatments were randomly assigned to the plots. The planting of Maize and Cowpea were similar. The field experiment consisted of 4 treatments and laid in a randomized complete block design in 3 replications. The treatments involved sole maize, sole cowpea, Alternate-row intercrop and as described in Table 1. Two local varieties were cultivated, maize (somtex variety) and cowpea (brown eye variety). The crops were planted with a spacing of 75 cm inter-row × 25 cm intra-row.

Table 1. Treatments Description

Treatment	Description
SC	Sole cowpea
SM	Sole maize
R1	Alternate-row intercrop
R2	Within-row intercrop

Data Collection

Data was collected throughout the entire growing season, with a particular emphasis on the following data:

1. Growth parameters:

These include measuring of plant height and number of leaves per plant.

2. Crop Yield:

The aggregate mass of the harvest was assessed for maize and cowpea in both integrated and separate plots.

3. Land use efficiency

Land use efficiency was determined by calculating Land equivalent ratio (LER) using (Mead and Willey, 1980) Formula.

$$LER = Y_{ab} / Y_{aa} + Y_{ba} / Y_{bb}$$

Where,

LER= Land equivalent ratio (LER)

Y_{Ia}= intercropping yield of crop A

Y_{pa}= pure standard yield of Crop A

Y_{Ib}= intercropping yield of crop B

Y_{pb}= pure standard yield of Crop B

$$LER = Y_{Ia} / y_{pa} + y_{ib} / y_{pb}$$

LER= 1: no advantage of intercrop

LER<1: intercropping reduces total yield

LER>1: intercropping increases total yield thus beneficial.

Data Analysis

Statistical approaches are employed to do a quantitative analysis of the data. An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was utilized to do data analysis to identify statistically significant differences in yields among the different treatments of intercropping Maize with Cowpea.

Results and Discussion

According to this study, the study found that there was no significant effect on the plant height of either crop. This study observed a similar phenomenon to the study reported by Wang, et al. (2020) that indicated the semi-arid Maize likely had less access to some of the resources when it was sown after cowpea. However, there was a notable difference in the

number of leaves per plant. Maize plants grown in intercropping conditions did not exhibit significant changes in leaf production compared to those grown alone. In contrast, cowpea plants grown in intercropping situations showed a significant increase in the number of leaves per plant. This disparity in leaf development could be attributed to competition for resources between the intercropped species. Cowpea, a vine-like plant, may have an advantage in

acquiring sunlight by extending its leaves above the maize canopy. By positioning its leaves in a more favorable position for photosynthesis, cowpeas can enhance their growth and productivity in the intercropping system (Table 2). This finding with contract with report of Eskandari and Ghanbari (2009) that reported yield reduction in cowpea and maize in maize-cowpea intercrops due lower plant densities.

Table 2. Effect of Intercropped Cowpea with Maize and Cowpea on Plant Height, and Number of Leaves per Plant

Treatment	Plant height(cm)	Number of leaves per plant		
		cowpea	Maize	cowpea
Sole Maize	210a		13a	
Sole Cowpea		80a		20a
Maize+ Cowpea	218a	750a	14a	35b
Cowpea + maize	217a	70a	13a	40c
LSD 5%	NS		NS	

There was a significant effect of intercropping on the plant yield of both maize and cowpea (Table 3). The study revealed that while sole cropping of maize resulted in the highest grain yield (4245.4 kg ha⁻¹), intercropping systems also yielded respectable results. This superior performance in sole cropping can be attributed to the higher plant density, maximizing resource utilization by minimizing competition for light, nutrients, and water. However, intercropping provided a viable. This study was in line agreement with Biruk and Anteneh (2021) those reported intercropping provided a significant viable result. Alternative, offering significant advantages in terms of biodiversity and resource management. Produced the highest maize grain yield among the intercropping systems (3727.6 kg ha⁻¹). This was closely followed by the within-row intercropping system (3670.3 kg ha-

1), where cowpea was planted within rows of maize. These intercropping systems, while exhibiting some competition between the two crops, mitigated the negative effects through reduced plant density in maize rows, ultimately contributing to substantial yields. Also, the highest cowpea grain yield was observed in the sole cowpea system (727.13 kg ha⁻¹). This was due to the absence of competition with maize for resources. The alternate-row intercropping system followed with a considerably lower yield (460.90 kg ha⁻¹), demonstrating a trade-off between maximizing maize yield and achieving a satisfactory cowpea yield. The within-row intercropping system yielded the lowest cowpea yield (364.60 kg ha⁻¹), likely due to increased competition from maize for nutrients, sunlight, and water.

Table. 3 Effect of Intercropped Cowpea and Maize on Yield

Treatments	yield kg/ha	
	Maize	Cowpea
Sole Maize	4245.4a	
Sole Cowpea		727.13a
Maize+Cowpea(alternate-Row intercrop)	3727.6b	460.90b
Cowpea + Maize(within-Row intercropping)	3670.3c	364.60c

Land Equivalent Ratio (LER)

LER is used indicator to evaluate the efficiency of intercropping systems.

It represents the relative yield of the intercropped system compared to the sole cropping of individual crops. An LER greater than 1 indicates that the intercropping system outperforms the sole cropping systems, signifying synergistic effects.

The land equivalent ratio (LER) was greater when maize intercropped with cowpea. The highest LER was obtained by growing alternate-row intercrop (1.51) followed by within-row intercropping (1.36) (Table 4). This indicates the performance of alternate-row intercropping compared to within-row intercropping by optimizing intercropping arrangements, planting densities, and other management practices, farmers can harness the synergistic benefits of this complementary system, leading to increased crop yields and improved land utilization.

Table 4. Land Equivalent Ratio (LER)

Treatments	yield kg/ha		LER
	Maize	Cowpea	
Sole Maize	4245.4a		
Sole Cowpea		727.13a	
Maize+Cowpea(alternate-Row intercrop)	3727.6b	460.90b	1.51
Cowpea + Maize(within-Row intercropping)	3670.3c	364.60c	1.36

Conclusion

In Aynayaskax Village, most smallholder farmers practice intercropping with cowpea and maize. Despite this, recent findings indicate that growing intercropping yields better results than separately. The study highlights that while intercropping improves resource use, boosts yields, and enhances soil quality, monoculture outperforms it in yield metrics. Intercropping offers benefits like improved soil health, especially through nitrogen fixation by cowpeas, which reduces the need for synthetic fertilizers. This can lower costs and environmental impact, addressing challenges such as soil fertility and water scarcity. Overall, the research advocates for broader adoption of intercropping in similar regions, as it supports sustainable agriculture, environmental conservation, and economic resilience. It suggests that other regions with similar conditions could benefit from this approach. Stakeholders, including farmers and NGOs, should promote intercropping to enhance productivity and sustainability, making efficient use of land resources.

Constraints and Challenges

- Heavy rainfall during the season in Gu led to severe flooding in Caynaskax Village, severely damaging all cultivated land, including demonstration farms. The floodwaters completely submerged maize and cowpea crops, destroying the entire harvest. The extensive flooding also led to a drastic reduction in cowpea yields.
- Furthermore, the village's remote location from the university staff office created logistical challenges for researchers overseeing activities on the demonstration farms. The frequent trips needed to monitor the research placed a strain on the already limited research budgets.
- Additionally, the flooding hindered access to the farms, delaying data collection and compromising the integrity of research findings.

Recommendations

- Farmers could consider adopting alternate-row intercropping for maize and cowpea, as it showed competitive maize yields while still providing reasonable cowpea yields. This system balances resource utilization effectively.

- The study suggests that local government entities and international agricultural development organizations should increase their assistance for intercropping practices.
- The study highlights the significance of creating and executing educational initiatives and workshops specifically designed for farmers in Aynayaskax Village and its neighboring villages. These programs should focus primarily on the advantages and methodologies of intercropping. Structured training sessions can effectively assist in the adoption and sustainability of intercropping systems by imparting information and practical skills.
- Conduct further research to explore different intercropping patterns or varieties that might enhance overall productivity without compromising individual crop yields and investigate the long-term effects of intercropping on soil health, pest management, and overall sustainability.

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